

CO-ORDINATION BETWEEN DIFFERENT METHODS OF SYNTHESIS OF DIHYDROFLAVANOLS AND THEIR STEREOCHEMISTRY

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Stereochemical configurations assigned in a previous publication to dihydroflavanols are further supported by dehydrogenation data. The methods of synthesis of dihydroflavanols have been correlated by synthesising the same dihydroflavanol by two different methods.

On the basis of the above findings, stereochemical configuration for both synthetic and natural dihydroflavanols is suggested. Incidentally, the conformations for C₇-OH and C₄-OH in melacacidin are tentatively assigned.

In previous communications (Kulkarni and Joshi, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 1421, 1456) synthesis of dihydroflavanols and flavan-3:4-diols was reported and for the first time Barton's concept of conformational analysis (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1027; *Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 21) was introduced in this field to elucidate their stereochemistry. Dihydropyran ring of dihydroflavanols or flavan-diols was compared with *cyclohexene* and it was pointed out that C₂ and C₃ positions in dihydropyran are identical with C₄ and C₅ carbon atoms in *cyclohexene*. The bonds of the C₂ and C₃ carbon atoms were designated as equatorial and axial, and this terminology was adopted to understand the stereochemistry of substituents on these carbon atoms. It is obvious that the same concept can be utilised to understand the stereochemistry of catechins. In fact, this conformational aspect has been accepted and recently stereochemical configurations of catechin (Clark-Lewis, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1955, 1218), epicatechin (Roberts, *ibid.*, 1955, 631) and melacacidin (King and Clark-Lewis, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3384) have been discussed in this direction.

Further, on the basis of the generalisation (Barton, *loc. cit.*) that, "a bulky substituent in a *cyclohexane* ring system takes up an equatorial conformation as it is energetically most favourable arrangement", an equatorial conformation for the side phenyl nucleus in the dihydroflavanol was assigned (Kulkarni and Joshi, *loc. cit.*). On reduction of 3':4':7:8-tetramethoxydihydroflavanol (IIb) with lithium aluminium hydride and catalytically, two compounds, m. p. 179° (XIIa) and 131-32° (XIIb), isomeric in position, "4", were isolated. The lower-melting compound, which was obtained in almost quantitative yield, when the dihydroflavanol was reduced catalytically in strongly acid

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medium, was in accordance with the generalisation of Barton (*loc. cit.*) presumed to have C₄-OH axial. The other isomer therefore has C₄-OH equatorial. Further, on the assumption that the Auwers-Skita rule (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1035) was applicable to these compounds, the higher-melting compound was assigned *trans* (2e, 3e, 4e) configuration and the lower-melting one as *cis* (2e, 3e, 4a) configuration (data such as velocity of hydrolysis of diacetates, behaviour of isomers on chromatographic column, formation of cyclic carbonate from the "*cis*" *i.e.* lower-melting isomer etc. supporting the above configurations will be published elsewhere). Thus, indirectly the conformation for C₃-OH group in the dihydroflavonol as equatorial was arrived at. This conformation for C₃-OH in dihydroflavonol was further supported by the fact that none of our diols were identical with (±) malacacidin tetramethyl ether (XIVa), synthesised by King and Clark-Lewis (*loc. cit.*) and assigned 2e, 3e, 4e conformation, which was also independently arrived at by us.

These investigations were further extended with a view to synthesising epimeric dihydroflavonol with C₃(OH) axial and thence the corresponding remaining two racemates of flavan-3:4-diols. It was thought that two 3-bromoflavanones, isomeric in position '3', recently reported by Limaye and co-workers (*Rasayanam*, 1950-52, 2, 1, 51), would serve as intermediates for this purpose. Accordingly, 6-methyl-4'-methoxy-3-bromoflavanone (Vb, m.p. 152°), obtained by bromination of the corresponding flavanone, and its isomer (Va, m.p. 138°), obtained by cyclisation of the corresponding 2'-acetoxy-chalkone dibromide (Ia), were synthesised. The stereochemical configurations of these 3-bromoflavanones will be reported elsewhere. Both these compounds on treatment with common reagents used for the replacement of bromine with hydroxy or acetoxy group should give different dihydroflavonols, but unfortunately they are easily dehydrobrominated to the same corresponding flavone. Similarly, the 3-bromoflavanone (Vc), obtained on bromination of 3':4':7:8-tetramethoxyflavanone (VIa) with *N*-bromosuccinimide, is dehydrobrominated to the corresponding flavone (IVb). Since this method

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was unsuitable for the synthesis of epimeric dihydroflavonol and thence the other two racemic flavandiols, all the methods for the synthesis of dihydroflavonols were reviewed. The identical dihydroflavonols were synthesised by two different methods and thus the methods were correlated. We have been so far unable to synthesise epimeric ($\pm$) 6-methyl-4'-methoxydihydroflavonol by any of these methods. However, the established co-ordination amongst the methods of synthesis and the dehydrogenation data on dihydroflavonols enable us to assign conformations to both synthetic and natural dihydroflavonols; this communication deals with this aspect of the chemistry of dihydroflavonols.

The following methods are generally used for the synthesis of dihydroflavonols:—

- (1) Flavanone $\xrightarrow{\text{Pb (OAc)}_4}$ dihydroflavonol (Oyamada, *J. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1943, **64**, 331, 471).
- (2) Chalkone $\xrightarrow{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{alkali}}$ dihydroflavonol (Murakami and Irie, *Proc. Imp. Acad. Tokyo*, 1935, **11**, 229; Riechel and Steudel, *Annalen*, 1942, **553**, 83).
- (3) Chalkone acetate $\xrightarrow{\text{Br}}$ dibromide $\xrightarrow{\text{acetone-sodium carbonate}}$ dihydroflavonol (Limaye, *Rasayanam*, 1950, **2** 1).
- (4) Diacetoxychalkone $\xrightarrow{\text{HCl}}$ dihydroflavonol (Oyamada, *J. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1934, **65**, 785)*.
- (5) Flavanol $\xrightarrow{\text{sodium hydrosulphite}}$ dihydroflavonol (Pew, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3031).
- (6) Flavanone $\xrightarrow{\text{halogen}}$ 3-halogenoflavanone $\xrightarrow{\text{AgOAc}}$ dihydroflavonol (Zemplen and Bogнар, *Ber.*, 1943, **76B**, 452; Seshadri *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1954, **39A**, 254).
- (7) Flavonol $\xrightarrow{\text{hydrogenation}}$ dihydroflavonol, flavandiol (King *et al.*, *Chem & Ind.*, 1954, 757; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 1399).

The same dihydroflavonol acetates, *i.e.*, 6-methyl-4'-methoxy-(VIIa) and 7:4'-dimethoxy-(VIIc), were synthesised by us by methods (1) and (3). Similarly ($\pm$) fustin trimethyl ether (VIIId), synthesised by Oyamada (*Annalen*, 1939, **533**, 441) by the method (4) and proved to be identical with the natural product, has also been obtained in this Laboratory by the method (3). Limaye and co-workers (*Rasayanam*, 1952, **2**, 51) reported the synthesis of the dihydroflavonol, *i.e.* 4'-methoxy-6-benzoyldihydroflavonol by methods (2) and (3). Synthetic ($\pm$) taxifolin, which, on the basis of dehydrogenation data, we think belongs to the first series, was obtained by the reduction of quercetin with sodium hydrosulphite (Pew, *loc. cit.*), *i.e.* by the method (5), and was shown to be identical with the natural one by Pew. We therefore believe that the dihydroflavonols synthesised by methods 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 belong to the same series, *i.e.*, C₂-phenyl and C₃-OH in them are equatorial. Such a configuration would be energetically most stable and therefore it is no wonder that all the above methods give dihydroflavonols which belong to the same series. Seshadri *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) observed that synthetic 3-hydroxy-naringenin (XI), obtained through 3-iodoflavanone, *i.e.*, by method (6), was different from

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the natural one (VIII) which, we believe, belongs to the first series (*vide infra*). Flavan-diols (Kulkarni and Joshi, *loc. cit.*) (XIIa) and (XIIIa), isomeric in position-4, synthesised by us from the corresponding dihydroflavonol, which is prepared by the method (3), are different from that (XIVa), synthesised by King *et al.* by hydrogenation of the corresponding flavonol (*private communication* from Dr. Clark-Lewis, for which we are grateful to him). It is therefore obvious that the flavan-diol of King is isomeric in position-3, *i.e.*, C₃-OH is axial and hence in the corresponding dihydroflavonol would also be axial. We therefore believe that the dihydroflavonols synthesised by methods (6) and (7) would belong to the second series (*i.e.* C₃-OH in them would be axial). Incidentally, this inference and the chemical evidence of King *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) that melacacidin forms a cyclic carbonate, enable us to suggest conformations for C₂-OH and C₄-OH in melacacidin as axial and equatorial respectively.

The above generalisations are supported by the dehydrogenation experiments carried out by us on some of the dihydroflavanols, synthesised in this laboratory and by Seshadri *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) on natural and synthetic 3-hydroxynaringenin. On boiling with alcoholic sulphuric acid, 6-methyl-4'-methoxydihydroflavanol (IIa m.p. 160°) (Kulkarni and Joshi, *loc. cit.*), 3':4':7:8-tetramethoxydihydroflavanol (IIb, m.p. 166°) (Kulkarni and Joshi, *loc. cit.*) and 3-hydroxynaringenin (VIII) (Seshadri *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) are dehydrogenated to 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavonol (IIIa, m.p. 192°) (Limaye, *loc. cit.*, p. 1), 3':4':7:8-tetramethoxyflavonol (IIIb, m.p. 221°) (Kostanecki and Rudse, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 935) and Kaempferol (IX) (Seshadri *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) respectively, while the epimeric dihydroflavonol-synthetic 3-hydroxynaringenin (XI) gets dehydrated to furnish epigenin (X) (Seshadri *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Mechanism suggested for dehydrogenation of dihydroflavonols by Asahina (*J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1928, 48, 1081) *i.e.*, C₂-H is oxidised to C₂-OH [in our opinion C₂-H(a) → C-OH(a) by radical mechanism] and dehydration between C₂-OH and C₃-H, *i.e.*, dehydrogenation of the original dihydroflavonol takes place, can be explained on *trans* (a, a)-elimination principle. Barton (*loc. cit.*) has reported that for ready 1:2-elimination reactions of ionic type, both the substituents in the cyclohexane system should be *trans* and axial. According to our hypothesis C₂-H(a) oxidised to C₂ OH(a) and C₃-H in the first series are *trans* and axial, and hence, dehydration product or dehydrogenation of dihydroflavanol should be favoured, as observed above. Recent observations of Robertson *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 4573) that 3-hydroxyflavanone prepared by the 'method (1) could not be dehydrated to the flavone further supports our hypothesis. In the second series C₂-H and C₃-OH are *trans* and axial, and hence, dehydration should be facilitated, as has been experimentally observed in the case of synthetic 3-hydroxynaringenin (Seshadri *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). Alkaline reagents (Gripenberg and Silander, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1955, 443 and the references cited therein) are rather drastic and likely to bring about isomerisation or epimerisation, and hence, dehydrogenation in their presence is not taken into consideration.

On the basis of the methods of synthesis and dehydrogenation data, the synthetic and natural dihydroflavanols, tabulated below, are provisionally assigned the following conformations. From Table I it can be inferred that naturally occurring dihydroflavonols belong to the first series. Wide occurrence in nature of these dihydroflavonols

i.e., with C₂-phenyl and C₃-OH, both equatorial, would be expected, as such an arrangement would be the most thermodynamically stable. In view of the relationship, recently established between alpinone (Kotake, Sakan and Kubota, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 1562) and pinobanksin (Lindstedt, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1950, 4, 772), we believe that the latter belongs to the same series as alpinone, which is synthesised by method (2), and hence, included in the first series. The dehydrogenation data (Lindstedt, *loc. cit.*) on pinobanksin, which suggests its inclusion in the second series, therefore probably requires recheck-up.

TABLE I

Dihydroflavanol.	Nature.	Method of synthesis.	Dehydrogenation or dehydration with H ₂ SO ₄ .	Conformation for C ₃ -OH.
<i>1st Series :</i>				
1. 6-Methyl-4'-methoxy ¹	Synthetic	2 & 3	Dehydrogenation	e
2. 7 : 4'-Dimethoxy ¹	"	2 & 3	Not known	e
3. 3' : 4' : 7 : 8-Tetramethoxy ¹	"	3	Dehydrogenation	e
4. 6-Benzoyl-4'-methoxy ⁴	"	1 & 3	Not known	e
5. Fustin trimethyl ether ⁵	"	3 & 4	Do	e
6. Taxifolin ⁶	Natural	...	Dehydrogenation	e
	Synthetic	5		
7. Dihydrorobinetin ⁷	Natural	...	Do	e
8. 3-Hydroxynaringenin ⁸	"	...	Do	e
9. Alpinone ⁹	"	...	Not known	e
	Synthetic	2		
10. Pigobanksin ⁹	Natural converted to alpinone ³		No dehydrogenation (?)	e
<i>2nd Series :</i>				
11. 3-Hydroxynaringenin ⁸	Synthetic	6	Dehydration	a
12. 3-Hydroxyhesperitin ⁹	Synthetic	6	Not known	a
1. Kulkarni & Joshi, <i>loc. cit.</i>	4. Limaye, <i>loc. cit.</i> , p. 51.	7. Freudenberg & Hartmann, <i>Annalen</i> 1954, 587, 207.		
2. Oyamada, <i>loc. cit.</i> , 1934	5. Oyamada, <i>loc. cit.</i> , 1939	8. Lindstedt, <i>loc. cit.</i>		
3. Kotake, <i>et al.</i> , <i>loc. cit.</i>	6. Pew, <i>loc. cit.</i>	9. Seshadri <i>et al.</i> , <i>loc. cit.</i>		

Attempts are being made to collect more data by synthesising a number of dihydroflavanols, particularly by methods (6) and (7). Ozonolysis experiments on dihydroflavanols are in progress with a view to assigning them both the relative and absolute configurations.

EXPERIMENTAL

6-Methyl-4'-methoxydihydroflavanol (IIa).—2'-Hydroxy-5'-methyl-4-methoxychalcone (m.p. 97-99°), prepared by the condensation of 2-acetyl-*p*-cresol and anisaldehyde, was acetylated and then brominated to dibromochalkone (Ia) (Auwers and Anschutz, *Ber.*, 1921, 54, 1543), m.p. 126°. It (1 g.) was then converted into the corresponding dihydroflavanol by boiling with aqueous acetone (10 c.c., 60%) for 10 minutes (Limaye, *loc. cit.*, p. 1) and then with sodium carbonate (10 c.c., 10%). On cooling, the oil separated and solidified. It was filtered and crystallised twice from alcohol, m.p. 160°, yield 0.4 g.

6-Methyl-4'-methoxy-3-acetoxyflavanone (VIIa): Method (1).—The dihydroflavanol (IIa: 200 mg.), dissolved in acetic anhydride (2 c.c.) and pyridine (1 c.c.), was kept overnight and then poured in water. The resulting solid was filtered and crystallised twice from alcohol, m.p. 133°, yield 0.15 g. (Limaye, *loc. cit.*, records m.p. 140°). (Found: C, 69.98; H, 5.63. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{18}O_5$: C, 69.94; H, 5.52%).

Method (2).—To a solution of 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavanone (m.p. 110°) 1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.) was added lead tetra-acetate (2.4 g., 1.5M) in small portions during 45 minutes. During this period the temperature was maintained at 80-90° and the mixture was further heated at the same temperature for 4 hours. It was poured in water, extracted with ether and the ethereal extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether evaporated. The residue was crystallised twice from alcohol, m.p. 133°, yield 60 mg. (Found: C, 70.08; H, 5.54. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{18}O_5$: C, 69.94; H, 5.52%). Mixed m.p. with the one obtained by method (1) showed no depression.

The mother-liquors of crystallisation were combined and evaporated. The residue was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-60°) when a compound melting at 170° was obtained in poor yield. This was identified as 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavone (IVa).

Dehydrogenation of (IIa).—The dihydroflavanol (IIa, 0.35 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (140 c.c.) and 4N- H_2SO_4 (35 c.c.) was added to it and refluxed in a current of oxygen for 24 hours, and the solvent evaporated. The residue was washed with water and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 192°, yield 0.22 g. It was identified as 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavonol (IIIa).

3-Bromo-6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavanone (Va)*.—2'-Acetoxy-5'-methyl-4-methoxy-chalkone dibromide (0.47 g.) was dissolved in warm dilute acetic acid (2 c.c., 85%) and kept overnight, when crystals separated. These were filtered, washed and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 138°, yield 0.25 g.

3-Bromo-6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavanone (Vb).**—6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavanone (1.08 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (2 c.c.) and to its boiling solution was added bromine in acetic acid (2.6 c.c., 25%). After two hours crystals separated, which were filtered, washed and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 152°, yield 1 g. (Found: C, 58.78; H, 4.59. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{12}O_3Br$: C, 58.8; H, 4.3%).

Action of NaOH solution on 3-Bromoflavanones.—(a). The alcoholic solutions of the 3-bromoflavanones (m.p. 138° and 152°) were treated with 10N-NaOH when a yellow precipitate separated in few minutes. It was filtered, washed with water, crystallised from alcohol and identified as the corresponding flavone, m.p. 170°.

(b). **Action of Potassium Acetate on the 3-Bromoflavanones.**—The alcoholic solutions of the above 3-bromoflavanones were refluxed with potassium acetate for 4 hours and poured in water. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol, and identified as the corresponding flavone, m.p. 170°.

* This was prepared by the method described in the Ph. D. thesis submitted to the University of Poona by G. V. Bhide.

** Melting point 152° could not be raised to 168°, as reported in the thesis.

(c). *Action of Silver Acetate on the 3-Bromoflavanones.*—The alcoholic solutions of the 3-bromoflavanones were refluxed with silver acetate for 4 hours and filtered. The solution was diluted and the precipitate was crystallised from alcohol. From the crystals, separated in the first crop, the bromo compounds were recovered unchanged. The mother-liquors were evaporated and the residue recrystallised from alcohol, when a little amount of the corresponding flavone, m.p. 170°, was obtained.

In the experiments carried out in acetic acid, the major product was 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavone, m.p. 170°.

2'-Acetoxy-3':4'-3:4-Tetramethoxychalkone (Ib).—The chalkone (m.p. 125-27°) (5 g.) was heated with fused sodium acetate (50 mg.) and acetic anhydride (8 c.c.) for one hour. The reaction mixture was poured in water and the resulting solid was filtered and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 125°. It gave no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride and was insoluble in dilute aqueous alkali. (Found: C, 65.48; H, 6.17; Calc. for C₂₁H₂₂O₇: C, 65.29; H, 5.69%).

3':4'-7:8-Tetramethoxydihydroflavanol (IIb).—The above chalkone (0.6 g.) was dissolved in CCl₄ (12.5 c.c.) and a solution of bromine in CCl₄ (1 c.c., 25%) was added. After two hours the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was boiled with aqueous acetone (80%, 10 c.c.) for 13-16 minutes and subsequently with sodium carbonate (10%, 10 c.c.) for 3 minutes. On cooling, the oil separated and solidified. It was filtered and crystallised twice from alcohol, m.p. 166°, yield 0.2 g. (Found: C, 63.55; H, 5.66. Calc. for C₁₉H₂₀O₇: C, 63.33; H, 5.55%).

It gave no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. It, however, gave an orange coloration with H₂SO₄ (conc.) and a pink coloration with alcoholic zinc-hydrochloric acid.

3':4'-7:8-Tetramethoxy-3-acetoxyflavanone (VIIb).—The dihydroflavanol (IIb: 200 mg.) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (4 c.c.) and pyridine (2 c.c.) and kept overnight. The solution was poured in water and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and the ether distilled over. The residue was crystallised thrice from 70% alcohol, m.p. 113-16° (100 mg.). (Found: C, 62.23; H, 5.94. Calc. for C₂₁H₂₂O₈: C, 62.69; H, 5.47%).

Dehydrogenation of (IIb).—The dihydroflavanol (IIb: 100 mg.) was dissolved in alcohol (15 c.c.) and 4*N*-H₂SO₄ (15 c.c.) was added to it. The solution was refluxed for 4 hours in a current of oxygen. It was cooled and the precipitate was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 221°, yield 40 mg. Mixed m.p. with 3':4'-7:8-tetramethoxyflavanol (IIb) (Kostanecki and Rudse, *loc. cit.*) gave no depression.

Bromination of 3':4'-7:8-Tetramethoxyflavanone and the Action of Silver Acetate on the Bromo Compound.—3':4'-7:8-Tetramethoxyflavanone (m.p. 144°) (0.8 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of CCl₄ and CHCl₃ (1:1; 40 c.c.) and *N*-bromosuccinimide (1*M*) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 30 minutes in presence of light and the resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with CCl₄ and dried, m.p. 175°, yield 0.2 g.

The bromo compound (Vc, 0.2 g.) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) and silver acetate (0.2 g.) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hours on a water-bath and 1 hour in an oil-bath (145-55°). It was filtered and the filtrate diluted with

cold water, when a precipitate was obtained. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 199-200°, yield 50 mg. Venkataraman *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1107) reported for 3':4'-7:8-tetramethoxyflavone (IVb), m.p. 199°.

The substance was free from bromine and gave a red coloration with alcoholic zinc-hydrochloric acid, and hence, a flavone. (Found: C, 66.77; H, 5.4. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$: C, 66.82; H, 5.26%).

7:4'-Dimethoxydihydroflavanol (IIc).—2'-Hydroxy-4:4'-dimethoxychalkone (m.p. 113-14°) (50 g.), prepared by the method of Kostanecki *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 322), was acetylated by boiling for 2 hours with acetic anhydride (2 c.c.) and fused sodium acetate (few mg.). The solution was cooled and acetic acid (0.5 c.c.) and bromine in acetic acid (1.12 c.c., 25%) were added to it. After two hours, the solution was diluted with water, when a white precipitate was obtained (900 mg.). It was boiled with aqueous acetone (10 c.c., 80%) for 15 minutes and subsequently with sodium carbonate (10 c.c., 10%) for 3 minutes. On cooling, the oil separated and solidified. It was filtered and crystallised thrice from alcohol (Ic), m.p. 133°, yield 200 mg. It gave no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride, but a violet colour with zinc-hydrochloric acid. (Found: C, 67.88; H, 5.27. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{16}O_6$: C, 68.0; H, 5.33%).

7:4-Dimethoxy-3-acetoxyflavanone (VIIc): Method (1).—7:4'-Dimethoxydihydroflavanol (0.2 g.) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (40 c.c.) and pyridine (1 c.c.) and kept overnight. The solution was poured in water and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated. The residue was crystallised thrice from alcohol, m.p. 140-42°. (Found C, 66.24; H, 5.19. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{18}O_6$: C, 66.66; H, 5.26%).

Method (2).—To a solution of 7:4'-dimethoxyflavanone (VIc, 0.8 g.) (Kostanecki and Juppen, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 4161) in acetic acid (50 c.c.) was added lead tetra-acetate (2 g.) in small portions and the same procedure was adopted as laid down under method (2) for (VIIa). The residue was crystallised twice from alcohol, m.p. 140-141°, yield 40 mg. Mixed m.p. with the one obtained by method (1) showed no depression. (Found: C, 66.41; H, 5.04. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{18}O_6$: C, 66.66; H, 5.26%).

The mother-liquors of crystallisation were combined and evaporated. The sticky residue was dissolved in minimum amount of benzene and the solution adsorbed over alumina. On elution with petroleum ether a substance melting at 144° was obtained in poor yield. It showed no depression in the mixed m.p. with 7:4'-dimethoxyflavone (IVc) (Tambor, *Ber.*, 1916, 49, 1704).

Fustin Trimethyl Ether (7:3':4'-Trimethoxydihydroflavanol) (IIId).—2'-Acetoxy-3:3:4'-trimethoxychalkone (Id, m.p. 87°), the starting material, was prepared by the method of Oyama (*Annalen*, 1939, 538, 441). This compound (0.6 g.) was dissolved in CCl_4 (10 c.c.) and bromine in CCl_4 (1.1 c.c., 25%) was added to it. After two hours the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was boiled with aqueous acetone (80%, 10 c.c.) for 13-15 minutes and subsequently with sodium carbonate solution (10 c.c., 10%) for 3 minutes. On cooling, the oil separated and solidified. It was filtered and crystallised thrice from alcohol, m.p. 143°, yield, 0.15 g. It gave a pink coloration with zinc-hydrochloric acid and no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 65.22; H, 5.54. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$: C, 65.45; H, 5.45%).

7 : 3' : 4'-Trimethoxy-3-acetoxyl-dihydroflavanol (VIId).—The dihydroflavanol (IIId : 0.2 g.) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (4 c.c.) and pyridine (1 c.c.) and kept overnight. The solution was poured in water and the product was extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated. The residue was crystallised twice from alcohol, m.p. 145°, yield, 0.15 g. (Found : C, 64.72 ; H, 5.36. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{20}O_7$: C, 64.51 ; H, 5.36%).

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